

FURTHER IMPROVEMENTS OF CFA 3.0 BY COMBINING INPAINTING AND PANSHARPENING TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Color Filter Array (CFA) has been widely used in digital cameras. There are many variants of CFAs in the literature. Recently, a new CFA known as CFA 3.0 was proposed by us and has been shown to yield reasonable performance as compared to some standard ones. In this paper, we investigate the use of inpainting algorithms to further improve the demosaicing performance of CFA 3.0. Six conventional and deep learning based inpainting algorithms were compared. Extensive experiments demonstrated that one algorithm improved over other approaches.

KEYWORDS

CFA 3.0, color filter array, demosaicing, inpainting, deep learning, pansharpening

1. INTRODUCTION

Bayer pattern [1] was invented in the early 1980's and is still a very popular color filter array (CFA) for digital cameras. The Bayer pattern as shown in Figure 1(a) is also known as CFA 1.0 in the literature. Even for planetary explorations, NASA has adopted the Bayer pattern in the Mastcam imagers onboard the Mars rover Curiosity [2]-[5].

Aiming to improve the Bayer pattern in low lighting conditions, Kodak researchers [6,7] invented a red-green-blue-white (RGBW) CFA pattern, which is also known as CFA 2.0, which is shown in Figure 1(b). Half of the pixels in CFA 2.0 are white and the remaining pixels share the R, G, and B colors. Due to the presence of white pixels, the camera sensitivity is increased and hence the performance of CFA 2.0 in low lighting conditions should be better than CFA 1.0. Extensive experiments in [8] showed that CFA 2.0 is indeed better than CFA 1.0 in low lighting conditions, where Poisson noise is dominant. Some additional studies were also carried out for CFA 2.0 [9].

In a recent paper by us [12], a new CFA pattern known as CFA 3.0 was proposed. In CFA 3.0 as shown in Figure 1(c), even more white pixels are introduced, hoping that the demosaicing performance will be further improved in low lighting conditions. Unfortunately, having more white pixels means that fewer color pixels will be present in the color filter array. Consequently, the overall performance of CFA 3.0 for low lighting images is slightly inferior to CFA 2.0 but still better than CFA 1.0 [10][11].

Figure 1. Three CFA patterns. (a) CFA 1.0; (b) CFA 2.0; (c) CFA 3.0.

In [12], we used an interpolation method known as local directional interpolation and nonlocal adaptive thresholding (LDI-NAT) [13] to create the luminance or panchromatic (pan) band. After that, the full resolution luminance band is then fused with the low resolution color image via pansharpening techniques to create the full resolution color image. The whole process is summarized in Figure 2. The luminance image is also termed the panchromatic image and we use them interchangeably in this paper.

Figure 2. A pansharpening approach for CFA 3.0.

From Figure 2, it is natural to ask several research questions. First, are there any methods that can further enhance the performance of the luminance image? As we will see in the experiments, the demosaicing performance can be improved quite a lot if the ground truth panchromatic image is used. This means that if one can apply a high performing interpolation method to fill in the missing pixels in the panchromatic band, then the overall demosaicing performance will be increased. Second, if there does exist a good interpolation/inpainting algorithm, how much performance gain can we achieve?

In this paper, we will focus on answering the two aforementioned questions. In particular, we propose to investigate various inpainting methods to create the panchromatic band. In addition to the LDI-NAT method, we also applied five other methods, including conventional and deep learning algorithms. After the inpainting is done, we then apply various pansharpening algorithms to generate the final demosaiced images. We extensively evaluate the different combinations using the Kodak benchmark images.

There are three major contributions in this paper:

- We are the first ones to apply various inpainting methods to generate the pan band for demosaicing CFA 3.0.
- We are also the first team to investigate the combination of inpainting and pansharpening in demosaicing CFA 3.0.
- The combination of inpainting and pansharpening results are better than before, but there is still room for further improvement.

The rest of our paper is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes the methods, data, and performance metrics. Section 3 presents all the experimental results. Finally, some concluding remarks and future directions will be given.

2. METHODS, DATA, AND PERFORMANCE METRICS

2.1. Architecture of Demosaicing CFA 3.0 with Inpainting and Pansharpening

In our earlier paper [12], we presented a standard approach to demosaicing CFA 3.0. For completeness, that architecture is depicted in Figure 3. The R, G, and B pixels in the CFA 3.0 are extracted to form a reduced resolution CFA image. A demosaicing algorithm (LDI-NAT) is used to demosaic it and generate a reduced resolution color image. Parallel to this activity, the white/panchromatic pixels in the CFA 3.0 are also interpolated to form the luminance image using the same LDI-NAT algorithm. The luminance image is then downsampled by two times via averaging and the reduced resolution luminance image is subtracted from the reduced resolution color image to generate the chrominance-luminance image. A simple upsampling via bicubic interpolation is then performed to generate the full resolution chrominance-luminance image. Finally, the luminance image and the chrominance-luminance image are added together to form the final demosaicing image. This simple architecture is very simple to understand and implement. Although there are many algorithms in the literature that could be used in the interpolation and demosaicing steps, we chose LDI-NAT in [12] simply because it has reasonable performance.

Figure 3. Standard demosaicing framework for CFA 3.0.

In this paper, we propose the architecture shown in Figure 4, which is essentially the same as the architecture shown in Figure 2 except the interpolation step. In Figure 4, we emphasize on the use

of inpainting algorithms for generating the luminance image and the other parts are exactly the same as Figure 2. The difference between interpolation and inpainting is very subtle. Normally, interpolation is used to fill in missing pixels in images that have regular missing patterns. On the other hand, inpainting is referring to missing pixels with free form patterns. That is, the missing patterns can have arbitrary shapes. As can be seen from Figure 4, the pansharpening step is to utilize the high resolution luminance image to sharpen the reduced resolution color image and the final pansharpened image will be the demosaiced image.

Figure 4. Proposed architecture for the combined inpainting and pansharpening demosaicing approach.

2.2. Inpainting Methods

In recent years, there are many new developments in inpainting. In this paper, we have evaluated the following six techniques:

- Linear Directional Interpolation and Nonlocal Adaptive Thresholding (LDI-NAT): This algorithm is a demosaicing algorithm. However, it can be used for both demosaicing as well as interpolation [13]. It has good performance in our earlier studies [8]. We used LDI-NAT in our earlier paper [12] and this will be the baseline for our inpainting investigations.
- Laplacian: This method [14] fills in each missing pixel using the Laplacian interpolation formula by finding the mean of the surrounding known values.
- Bilinear: This method simply uses the average of neighboring pixels to fill in the missing pixels. Bilinear and Laplacian have similar performance.
- Inpaint_nans: We denote this as “inpaint” in our later experiments. This method was developed by D’Errico[15]. This is a very simple method that only uses the neighboring pixels to estimate the missing pixels which will be referred as NaNs (not a number).
- FOE: The Field of Experts method (FOE) was developed by Roth [16]. This method uses pre-trained models that are used to filter out noise and obstructions in images.
- Generative Inpainting (GenIn)[17]: A new inpainting method, Generative Inpainting (GenIn), which is a deep learning-based method [17], was considered in our research. It was developed at the University of Illinois that aims to outperform typical deep learning methods that use convolutional neural network (CNN) models. GenIn builds on CNN and Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) in an effort to encourage cohesion between created and existing pixels. GenIn ranked the first in one Github page (<https://github.com/1900zyh/Awesome-Image-Inpainting>), which contains many conventional and deep learning based algorithms. This is the reason we chose GenIn in this paper.

2.3. Pansharpening Methods

In the paper [18] written by us, we proposed a pansharpening approach to demosaicing CFA 2.0. This approach is illustrated in Figure 4. The missing pixels in the panchromatic band are interpolated. At the same time, the reduced resolution CFA is demosaiced. We then apply pansharpening to generate the full resolution color image. There are many pansharpening algorithms that can be used. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [19], Smoothing Filter-based Intensity Modulation (SFIM) [20], Modulation Transfer Function Generalized Laplacian Pyramid (GLP) [21], MTF-GLP with High Pass Modulation (HPM) [22], Gram Schmidt (GS) [23], GS Adaptive (GSA) [24], Guided Filter PCA (GFPCA) [25], PRACS [26] and hybrid color mapping (HCM) [27]-[31] have been used in our experiments. The list is a representative, if not exhaustive, set of competitive pansharpening algorithms.

2.4. Data

We downloaded a benchmark data set (Kodak) from a website (<http://r0k.us/graphics/kodak/>) and selected 12 images, which are shown in Figure 5. It should be noted that this dataset is well-known and has been used by many authors in the demosaicing community such as [32]-[36]. These clean images will be used as reference images for objective performance metrics generation. Moreover, they will be used for generating noisy images that emulate low lighting conditions.

Image 1

Image 2

Image 3

Image 4

Image 5

Image 6

Image 7

Image 8

Image 9

Image 10

Image 11

Image 12

Figure 5. Twelve clean images from the Kodak dataset.

2.5. Metrics

Five performance metrics were used in our experiments to compare the different methods and CFAs. These metrics are well-known in the literature.

- Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) [37]

Separate PSNRs in dBs are computed for each band. A combined PSNR is the average of the PSNRs of the individual bands. Higher PSNR values imply higher image quality.

- Structural SIMilarity (SSIM)
In [38], SSIM was defined to measure the closeness between two images. An SSIM value of 1 means that the two images are the same.
- Human Visual System (HVS) metric
Details of HVS metric in dB can be found in [39]. Higher values imply better results.
- HVSm (HVS with masking) [40]
Similar to HVS, HVS incorporates the visual masking effects in computing the metrics. Higher values imply better results.
- CIELAB

We also used CIELAB [41] for assessing demosaicing and denoising performance in our experiments. Smaller values mean good results.

It should be noted that the HVS and HVSm have better correlation with human perceptions than the other three metrics [42][43].

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we will first compare the performance of different inpainting algorithms on the generation of panchromatic bands. This step is critical for the overall performance of the demosaicing process. We will then focus on several case studies based on the performance of the inpainting results. In particular, we will generate the demosaicing results using the best inpainting method, the previous interpolation method of LDI-NAT in our earlier paper [12], and the ideal case of using the ground truth panchromatic band for inpainting.

3.1. Comparing Different Inpainting methods for Pan Band Generation

Here, we will focus on comparing the six different inpainting methods on each image from the KODAK dataset using the CFA3 pattern. For ease of exposition, we only used PSNR. The PSNR is calculated by comparing each inpainted result with the Ground Truth (Reference) pan image, which is generated by taking the average of the RGB bands in the original Kodak image. Table 1 summarizes the PSNR metrics of six inpainting algorithms using the 12 Kodak images. The missing pattern is the CFA 3.0 where 25% of the pixels in the panchromatic bands are missing. Figure 6 shows the averaged PSNR metrics of the five inpainting algorithms. We have the following observations:

- The method of LDI (LDI-NAT), which was used in our earlier paper [12], did not yield the best performance. It is 0.92 dB lower than the best performance algorithm (FOE).
- The deep learning method (GenIn) has a mediocre performance, which may be a little surprising because we had high expectation for it. We think that GenIn may be more

suitable for free-form missing clusters where big chunks of missing blocks with irregular shapes are present in images.

- FOE yielded the best performance, which is somewhat surprising because it was developed long time ago.

Table 1. Bilinear is the same as Laplacian. Inpainting results for 12 panchromatic images using five algorithms.

	Inpaint	FOE	Laplace	LDI	Bilinear	Generative
Img1	47.93	48.00	46.64	45.54	46.64	45.19
Img2	41.06	42.09	39.75	40.61	39.75	41.34
Img3	46.01	46.50	44.45	44.50	44.45	43.85
Img4	39.16	40.47	37.83	39.56	37.83	39.27
Img5	45.44	46.23	43.74	44.20	43.74	45.92
Img6	42.53	43.08	41.35	41.87	41.35	41.19
Img7	43.72	44.76	42.15	42.62	42.15	42.01
Img8	41.78	42.76	40.56	41.79	40.57	41.43
Img9	44.10	44.45	43.29	43.32	43.29	42.44
Img10	41.62	41.68	40.88	41.13	40.88	41.21
Img11	42.85	42.83	42.05	42.08	42.05	42.04
Img12	41.10	40.88	40.32	40.70	40.33	40.16
Average	43.11	43.25	41.92	42.33	41.92	42.17

Figure 6. Averaged PSNR of five inpainting algorithms.

3.2. Pansharpening Results using Different Inpainting methods

In this section, we will summarize three representative case studies. First, we will summarize the demosaicing results of an earlier approach in which applied LDI-NAT for interpolation the pan band. This will form the baseline for comparisons. Second, we will summarize the demosaicing results using the best inpainting method (FOE) based on results in Section 3.1. Third, we will summarize the ideal demosaicing results where the ground truth pan images are used in the demosaicing process.

3.2.1. LDI-NAT + Pansharpening

Here, the pan images were generated using LDI-NAT. After that, 11 pansharpening algorithms were applied to demosaic the 12 Kodak images. Table 2 summarizes all the performance metrics

of those 12 images. For easier interpretation of those numbers in Table 2, Figure 7 shows the bar charts of the averaged performance metrics. In terms of PSNR, the best performing method is the GSA method. However, GFPCA achieved the highest performance in CIELAB, HVS, and HVS_m. In particular, GFPCA is 3 dBs better than all the other methods in terms HVS and HVS_m and this is remarkable. The “standard” method has the best score in terms of SSIM. However, the difference is very small between the “standard” method and others. As mentioned earlier in Section 2, the PSNR and SSIM metrics do not necessarily match well with human perception. This turns out to be indeed the case. From those images in Figure 8, one can easily conclude that the GFPCA results have less artifacts and look closer to the ground truth images. The HVS and HVS_m metrics corroborate the above subjective evaluations results.

Table 2. Demosaicing results of Kodak images. LDI-NAT was used to generate the pan images.

Image		Baseline	Standard	GSA	HCM	SFI M	PCA	GFPCA	GLP	HPM	GS	PRACS	Best Score
Img1	PSNR	31.936	33.894	34.126	33.526	33.123	33.828	33.158	33.810	33.066	34.130	33.466	34.130
	Ciela b	2.659	2.374	2.393	2.481	2.699	2.445	2.773	2.429	2.724	2.351	2.453	2.351
	SSIM	0.739	0.859	0.854	0.831	0.838	0.845	0.806	0.853	0.834	0.858	0.820	0.859
	HVS	28.233	27.610	28.438	28.309	28.453	28.48	27.947	28.353	28.468	28.403	28.407	28.481
Img2	HVS _m	29.767	29.031	29.881	29.830	29.975	29.934	28.834	29.822	29.983	29.836	29.868	29.983
	PSNR	26.771	30.585	30.581	30.211	29.918	30.406	30.136	30.089	29.896	30.521	30.230	30.585
	Ciela b	4.860	3.766	3.803	3.874	3.901	3.891	3.219	3.906	3.904	3.830	3.903	3.219
	SSIM	0.685	0.868	0.867	0.856	0.856	0.845	0.823	0.857	0.853	0.850	0.852	0.868
Img3	HVS	23.976	24.331	24.486	24.304	24.264	24.726	27.637	24.398	24.228	24.403	24.445	27.637
	HVS _m	25.515	25.629	25.803	25.665	25.666	26.076	29.840	25.721	25.613	25.703	25.762	29.840
	PSNR	30.815	33.017	32.997	32.156	32.420	32.995	34.055	32.698	32.395	33.037	32.648	34.055
	Ciela b	3.758	3.378	3.313	3.535	3.432	3.324	2.949	3.345	3.459	3.303	3.398	2.949
Img4	SSIM	0.786	0.888	0.884	0.870	0.879	0.877	0.873	0.878	0.873	0.877	0.870	0.888
	HVS	27.087	27.099	27.266	27.081	27.211	27.403	29.897	27.192	27.218	27.366	27.221	29.897
	HVS _m	28.861	28.734	28.928	28.894	28.976	29.065	31.435	28.870	28.973	29.023	28.900	31.435
	PSNR	22.762	26.980	27.496	27.090	26.808	26.884	26.873	26.762	26.771	26.884	26.933	27.496
Img5	Ciela b	7.484	5.434	5.327	5.178	5.314	5.662	4.841	5.664	5.364	5.644	5.371	4.841
	SSIM	0.752	0.925	0.925	0.919	0.915	0.901	0.891	0.913	0.911	0.903	0.913	0.925
	HVS	20.315	20.370	21.077	21.064	21.160	20.986	24.117	21.095	21.203	20.867	20.918	24.117
	HVS _m	21.997	21.682	22.476	22.526	22.656	22.377	26.303	22.547	22.706	22.240	22.337	26.303
Img6	PSNR	30.816	34.107	33.952	33.686	33.558	33.825	34.541	33.694	33.469	34.132	33.766	34.541
	Ciela b	2.568	2.100	2.172	2.054	2.107	2.180	1.914	2.132	2.123	2.070	2.136	1.914
	SSIM	0.668	0.868	0.852	0.859	0.859	0.845	0.798	0.855	0.852	0.859	0.838	0.868
	HVS	27.733	27.824	28.155	28.083	28.083	28.344	30.514	28.154	28.083	28.132	28.146	30.514
Img7	HVS _m	29.444	29.335	29.707	29.676	29.772	29.912	32.085	29.750	29.775	29.662	29.688	32.085
	PSNR	27.706	30.874	31.031	30.391	30.382	30.980	31.381	30.647	30.278	30.926	30.601	31.381
	Ciela b	5.555	4.605	4.721	4.528	4.464	4.657	3.797	4.619	4.544	4.698	4.575	3.797
	SSIM	0.711	0.896	0.879	0.877	0.881	0.864	0.848	0.882	0.873	0.860	0.869	0.896
Img8	HVS	24.678	24.823	25.114	24.877	25.031	25.034	27.599	25.159	25.047	25.097	24.967	27.599
	HVS _m	26.353	26.293	26.606	26.470	26.603	26.520	29.306	26.665	26.611	26.591	26.495	29.306
	PSNR	30.446	34.517	34.469	34.081	33.701	34.351	33.767	33.917	33.680	34.391	34.183	34.517
	Ciela b	3.639	2.751	2.773	2.809	2.855	2.799	2.501	2.854	2.857	2.785	2.841	2.501

	b												
	SSIM	0.731	0.904	0.903	0.896	0.894	0.897	0.853	0.894	0.891	0.897	0.892	0.904
	HVS	27.968	28.395	28.40 9	28.32 3	28.19 9	28.49 7	32.017	28.32 1	28.15 9	28.41 1	28.415	32.017
	HVS m	29.538	29.687	29.69 6	29.66 1	29.57 9	29.80 0	34.461	29.62 8	29.51 7	29.70 6	29.727	34.461
Img8	PSN R	26.939	30.748	31.07 8	30.41 9	30.25 3	30.56 8	30.319	30.39 0	30.12 3	30.67 0	30.439	31.078
	Ciela b	4.697	3.707	3.566	3.769	3.704	3.758	3.200	3.746	3.734	3.707	3.812	3.200
	SSIM	0.733	0.900	0.899	0.885	0.890	0.883	0.860	0.891	0.886	0.888	0.877	0.900
	HVS	24.460	24.087	25.01 3	24.85 4	24.96 9	25.03 9	28.845	25.00 4	24.99 6	24.86 6	24.883	28.845
	HVS m	26.141	25.461	26.45 3	26.37 8	26.49 6	26.47 3	30.948	26.47 6	26.51 9	26.27 7	26.335	30.948
Img9	PSN R	29.775	32.268	32.68 2	32.11 7	31.74 2	32.67 6	33.783	32.31 6	31.66 9	32.66 8	32.318	33.783
	Ciela b	3.062	2.705	2.592	2.601	2.911	2.561	2.202	2.669	2.974	2.566	2.595	2.202
	SSIM	0.508	0.634	0.637	0.623	0.623	0.582	0.615	0.577	0.564	0.582	0.616	0.637
	HVS	26.329	26.028	26.75 3	26.63 2	26.80 8	26.74 8	30.150	26.82 3	26.82 0	26.77 9	26.621	30.150
	HVS m	27.955	27.482	28.23 4	28.18 1	28.36 2	28.22 8	31.987	28.33 1	28.36 5	28.26 4	28.115	31.987
Img10	PSN R	27.054	30.354	30.54 7	29.97 0	29.88 5	30.35 0	31.177	30.01 4	29.82 2	30.30 9	30.118	31.177
	Ciela b	4.808	3.975	3.930	3.927	3.915	3.991	3.223	4.075	3.940	3.959	3.936	3.223
	SSIM	0.687	0.867	0.867	0.856	0.857	0.832	0.802	0.858	0.853	0.855	0.848	0.867
	HVS	24.184	24.135	24.51 7	24.44 0	24.45 9	24.45 0	28.393	24.50 8	24.44 1	24.51 5	24.458	28.393
	HVS m	25.796	25.521	25.92 8	25.96 3	25.96 9	25.86 7	30.357	25.93 1	25.93 6	25.93 5	25.910	30.357
Img11	PSN R	29.027	32.011	32.23 4	31.70 3	31.70 7	32.12 1	31.682	31.83 5	31.65 5	32.14 3	31.687	32.234
	Ciela b	4.282	3.556	3.529	3.654	3.606	3.545	3.412	3.628	3.627	3.543	3.605	3.412
	SSIM	0.722	0.882	0.883	0.866	0.875	0.875	0.840	0.875	0.871	0.876	0.862	0.883
	HVS	26.763	26.320	27.14 3	27.13 4	27.17 5	27.08 0	28.744	27.17 7	27.21 5	27.08 5	27.089	28.744
	HVS m	28.417	27.778	28.62 6	28.70 8	28.72 4	28.54 8	30.402	28.69 3	28.76 2	28.55 2	28.586	30.402
Img12	PSN R	25.845	28.451	29.11 5	28.77 9	28.76 9	28.79 6	29.171	28.80 7	28.73 3	28.78 2	28.712	29.171
	Ciela b	4.525	3.669	3.558	3.610	3.621	3.786	3.176	3.707	3.649	3.783	3.620	3.176
	SSIM	0.770	0.909	0.910	0.903	0.902	0.880	0.883	0.891	0.889	0.880	0.902	0.910
	HVS	24.168	23.290	24.59 0	24.67 4	24.65 8	24.38 4	27.561	24.58 4	24.65 2	24.38 5	24.521	27.561
	HVS m	25.807	24.728	26.10 0	26.21 9	26.22 7	25.84 2	29.625	26.11 5	26.21 1	25.84 3	26.026	29.625
Average	PSN R	28.324	31.484	31.69 2	31.17 8	31.02 2	31.48 2	31.670	31.24 8	30.96 3	31.55 0	31.258	31.692
	Ciela b	4.325	3.502	3.473	3.502	3.544	3.550	3.101	3.564	3.575	3.520	3.520	3.101
	SSIM	0.708	0.867	0.863	0.853	0.856	0.844	0.824	0.852	0.846	0.849	0.846	0.867
	HVS	25.491	25.359	25.91 3	25.81 5	25.87 2	25.93 1	28.618	25.89 7	25.87 8	25.85 9	25.841	28.618
	HVS m	27.132	26.780	27.37 0	27.34 7	27.41 7	27.38 7	30.465	27.37 9	27.41 4	27.30 3	27.312	30.465

Figure 7. Averaged performance metrics of all the demosaicing results for the LDI-DAT case.

Figure 8. The ground truth image and three selected demosaiced images using the LDI-NAT inpainting method for pan band.

3.2.2. FOE + Pansharpening

In Section 3.1, we observed that the FOE algorithm yielded the best inpainting performance. Here, we show the demosaicing results of the 12 Kodak images by a combination of FOE and various pansharpening algorithms. Table 3 summarizes all the performance metrics of those 12 images. Figure 7 shows the bar charts of the averaged performance metrics. It can be seen that GFPCA achieved the highest performance in PSNR, CIELAB, HVS, and HVSm. Similar to the LDI-NAT case, GFPCA is 3 dBs better than all the other methods in terms HVS and HVSm. From those images in Figure 10, one can easily conclude that the GFPCA results have less artifacts and look closer to the ground truth images.

Table 3. Demosaicing results of Kodak images. FOE was used to generate the pan images.

Image		Baseline	Standard	GSA	HCM	SFIM	PCA	GFP	GLP	HPM	GS	PRAC	Best
								A				S	Score
Img1	PSNR	32.004	33.988	34.241	33.621	33.150	33.990	33.320	33.897	33.090	34.295	33.591	34.295
	Ciela b	2.651	2.347	2.387	2.460	2.700	2.412	2.756	2.408	2.728	2.321	2.434	2.321
	SSIM	0.741	0.858	0.851	0.830	0.833	0.847	0.807	0.849	0.829	0.858	0.821	0.858
	HVS	28.147	27.283	28.239	28.064	28.206	28.291	28.034	28.096	28.183	28.220	28.264	28.291
Img2	HVS m	29.690	28.717	29.694	29.606	29.741	29.756	28.878	29.589	29.720	29.665	29.735	29.756
	PSNR	26.836	30.908	30.855	30.446	30.112	30.747	30.393	30.119	29.876	30.867	30.569	30.908
	Ciela b	4.834	3.636	3.693	3.745	3.791	3.751	3.145	3.848	3.845	3.688	3.777	3.145
	SSIM	0.690	0.879	0.879	0.867	0.865	0.858	0.831	0.863	0.860	0.862	0.865	0.879
Img3	HVS	23.926	24.215	24.322	24.125	24.023	24.577	27.851	24.110	23.877	24.253	24.344	27.851
	HVS m	25.455	25.458	25.613	25.459	25.398	25.886	29.896	25.434	25.270	25.519	25.615	29.896
	PSNR	30.836	33.074	32.982	32.147	32.424	33.112	34.350	32.723	32.312	33.153	32.656	34.350
	Ciela b	3.748	3.328	3.316	3.492	3.434	3.243	2.901	3.292	3.469	3.223	3.376	2.901
Img4	SSIM	0.788	0.887	0.880	0.869	0.877	0.881	0.875	0.877	0.871	0.881	0.869	0.887
	HVS	26.942	26.720	26.877	26.635	26.789	27.048	30.071	26.794	26.752	27.015	26.941	30.071
	HVS m	28.725	28.377	28.564	28.479	28.577	28.731	31.491	28.505	28.541	28.694	28.639	31.491
	PSNR	22.785	27.014	27.530	27.124	26.806	26.938	26.852	26.696	26.677	26.939	27.069	27.530
Img5	Ciela b	7.453	5.324	5.249	5.054	5.216	5.552	4.810	5.638	5.315	5.534	5.246	4.810
	SSIM	0.754	0.930	0.929	0.923	0.919	0.907	0.894	0.916	0.914	0.908	0.918	0.930
	HVS	20.284	20.307	21.038	20.982	21.080	20.941	24.156	21.027	21.078	20.823	20.890	24.156
	HVS m	21.962	21.621	22.424	22.444	22.565	22.312	26.236	22.474	22.578	22.177	22.287	26.236
Img6	PSNR	30.856	34.218	33.821	33.785	33.588	33.980	34.732	33.675	33.420	34.305	33.835	34.732
	Ciela b	2.559	2.075	2.240	2.027	2.105	2.136	1.892	2.134	2.134	2.025	2.142	1.892
	SSIM	0.670	0.863	0.840	0.853	0.850	0.844	0.798	0.846	0.843	0.857	0.832	0.863
	HVS	27.696	27.709	28.050	28.017	27.964	28.309	30.640	28.068	27.924	28.097	28.107	30.640
Img7	HVS m	29.403	29.199	29.585	29.601	29.652	29.864	32.091	29.660	29.627	29.613	29.629	32.091
	PSNR	27.731	30.919	31.046	30.401	30.348	31.096	31.422	30.597	30.138	31.031	30.702	31.422
	Ciela b	5.532	4.540	4.814	4.458	4.441	4.505	3.772	4.588	4.562	4.551	4.531	3.772
	SSIM	0.716	0.903	0.880	0.884	0.885	0.878	0.853	0.885	0.874	0.874	0.875	0.903
Img8	HVS	24.581	24.559	24.929	24.608	24.786	24.868	27.678	24.942	24.755	24.922	24.830	27.678
	HVS m	26.256	26.028	26.410	26.225	26.368	26.343	29.303	26.449	26.337	26.405	26.348	29.303
	PSNR	30.510	34.925	34.820	34.376	33.902	34.788	34.014	33.962	33.648	34.827	34.604	34.925
	Ciela b	3.618	2.651	2.683	2.705	2.770	2.686	2.454	2.815	2.814	2.669	2.738	2.454
Img9	SSIM	0.736	0.912	0.910	0.904	0.901	0.907	0.859	0.899	0.896	0.908	0.901	0.912
	HVS	27.928	28.319	28.313	28.148	27.992	28.420	32.321	28.111	27.822	28.333	28.377	32.321
	HVS m	29.493	29.546	29.542	29.457	29.333	29.658	34.585	29.388	29.172	29.565	29.622	34.585
	PSNR	26.974	30.834	31.219	30.493	30.309	30.797	30.476	30.402	30.104	30.900	30.598	31.219
Img9	Ciela b	4.685	3.669	3.517	3.725	3.669	3.681	3.179	3.728	3.714	3.626	3.761	3.179
	SSIM	0.735	0.900	0.900	0.886	0.889	0.887	0.860	0.890	0.884	0.892	0.879	0.900
	HVS	24.405	23.909	24.904	24.704	24.818	24.954	28.973	24.850	24.809	24.787	24.798	28.973
	HVS m	26.086	25.295	26.357	26.259	26.365	26.400	30.940	26.353	26.370	26.211	26.246	30.940
PSNR	29.800	32.236	32.677	32.077	31.577	32.737	33.914	32.257	31.447	32.727	32.338	33.914	

				2	8	5	5		5	7	8		4
	Ciela b	3.052	2.674	2.587	2.570	2.927	2.506	2.174	2.648	2.998	2.506	2.576	2.174
	SSIM	0.511	0.634	0.637	0.623	0.622	0.587	0.615	0.578	0.563	0.588	0.621	0.637
	HVS	26.255	25.799	26.58	26.41	26.60	26.59	30.276	26.65	26.58	26.62	26.500	30.27
	HVS m	27.881	27.266	28.06	27.97	28.16	28.07	31.999	28.16	28.14	28.11	27.988	31.99
Img10	PSNR	27.087	30.381	30.56	29.94	29.83	30.47	31.298	29.92	29.66	30.42	30.217	31.29
	Ciela b	4.788	3.932	3.912	3.872	3.883	3.899	3.190	4.071	3.936	3.874	3.879	3.190
	SSIM	0.690	0.867	0.867	0.855	0.855	0.838	0.806	0.855	0.849	0.858	0.849	0.867
	HVS	24.051	23.775	24.23	24.03	24.06	24.20	28.526	24.17	23.97	24.25	24.241	28.52
	HVS m	25.663	25.177	25.64	25.60	25.59	25.60	30.328	25.60	25.51	25.66	25.688	30.32
Img11	PSNR	29.048	32.024	32.24	31.67	31.69	32.22	31.708	31.77	31.55	32.24	31.757	32.24
	Ciela b	4.268	3.513	3.500	3.617	3.577	3.476	3.394	3.603	3.611	3.473	3.560	3.394
	SSIM	0.726	0.886	0.887	0.870	0.878	0.883	0.843	0.877	0.873	0.884	0.867	0.887
	HVS	26.669	26.089	26.90	26.81	26.90	26.87	28.814	26.88	26.88	26.88	26.905	28.81
	HVS m	28.329	27.577	28.41	28.43	28.48	28.36	30.422	28.43	28.47	28.37	28.416	30.42
Img12	PSNR	25.869	28.419	29.10	28.71	28.70	28.86	29.150	28.73	28.62	28.85	28.744	29.15
	Ciela b	4.506	3.609	3.494	3.555	3.569	3.662	3.149	3.669	3.613	3.660	3.558	3.149
	SSIM	0.773	0.915	0.917	0.908	0.907	0.891	0.888	0.895	0.893	0.892	0.908	0.917
	HVS	24.036	22.977	24.30	24.32	24.34	24.14	27.476	24.24	24.28	24.15	24.266	27.47
	HVS m	25.658	24.416	25.77	25.84	25.87	25.57	29.381	25.75	25.81	25.58	25.732	29.38
Average	PSNR	28.361	31.578	31.75	31.23	31.03	31.64	31.802	31.23	30.87	31.71	31.390	31.80
	Ciela b	4.308	3.441	3.449	3.440	3.507	3.459	3.068	3.537	3.561	3.429	3.465	3.068
	SSIM	0.711	0.870	0.865	0.856	0.857	0.851	0.827	0.852	0.846	0.855	0.851	0.870
	HVS	25.410	25.138	25.72	25.57	25.63	25.76	28.735	25.66	25.57	25.69	25.705	28.73
	HVS m	27.050	26.556	27.17	27.11	27.17	27.21	30.463	27.15	27.13	27.13	27.162	30.46

(a) PSNR

(b) CIELAB

(c) SSIM

(d) HVS and HVS m

Figure 9. Averaged performance metrics of all the demosaicing results for the FOE inpainting case.

Figure 10. The ground truth image and three selected demosaiced images using the FOE inpainting method for pan band.

3.2.3. REF + Pansharpening

It will be important to show the best achievable demosaicing performance of those 12 Kodak images using CFA 3.0. The gap between this ideal case and what we have so far will indicate the room for further improvement. To generate the ideal demosaicing results, we used the ground truth pan images, which are generated by taking the average of the RGB bands in the original clean Kodak images. Table 4 summarizes the performance metrics for all the demosaicing results. Figure 11 plots the averaged metrics. The GFPCA has the best metrics in CIELAB, HVS, and HVSm. GSA has the best performance in terms of PSNR and the Standard method achieved the best in SSIM. From Figure 12, it is quite obvious that GFPCA has the least artifacts.

Table 4. Demosaicing results of Kodak images. Ground truth pan images were used in the pansharpening process.

Image		Baseline	Standard	GSA	HCM	SFI M	PCA	GFPCA	GLP	HPM	GS	PRACS	Best Score
Img1	PSNR	32.056	34.252	34.539	33.878	33.385	34.273	33.601	34.119	33.218	34.597	33.816	34.597
	Cielab	2.635	2.261	2.311	2.382	2.635	2.333	2.688	2.340	2.673	2.236	2.376	2.236
	SSIM	0.746	0.896	0.888	0.866	0.873	0.885	0.837	0.891	0.869	0.896	0.848	0.896
	HVS	28.179	27.292	28.313	28.130	28.260	28.363	28.112	28.145	28.232	28.291	28.332	28.363
Img2	PSNR	29.715	28.701	29.730	29.642	29.762	29.789	28.899	29.610	29.743	29.698	29.771	29.789
	PSNR	26.887	31.613	31.551	31.053	30.669	31.432	30.835	30.624	30.339	31.561	31.213	31.613
	Cielab	4.810	3.436	3.499	3.548	3.608	3.568	3.040	3.691	3.684	3.501	3.594	3.040
	SSIM	0.695	0.906	0.906	0.893	0.892	0.881	0.851	0.890	0.886	0.886	0.890	0.906
Img3	HVS	23.982	24.346	24.464	24.269	24.146	24.723	28.156	24.225	23.989	24.387	24.496	28.156
	HVS	25.505	25.515	25.679	25.541	25.458	25.947	30.070	25.486	25.331	25.578	25.692	30.070
	PSNR	30.887	33.356	33.255	32.333	32.621	33.407	34.886	32.951	32.476	33.451	32.908	34.886
	Cielab	3.734	3.248	3.236	3.412	3.341	3.161	2.819	3.217	3.384	3.141	3.308	2.819
Img4	SSIM	0.792	0.920	0.913	0.900	0.910	0.911	0.899	0.910	0.904	0.911	0.898	0.920
	HVS	26.958	26.684	26.880	26.622	26.746	27.058	30.303	26.773	26.697	27.025	26.971	30.303
	HVS	28.736	28.311	28.539	28.449	28.506	28.711	31.578	28.459	28.466	28.673	28.641	31.578
	PSNR	22.850	27.850	28.547	28.011	27.609	27.718	27.470	27.378	27.368	27.709	27.906	28.547

	Ciela b	7.419	5.037	4.972	4.729	4.929	5.327	4.629	5.412	5.052	5.306	4.978	4.629
	SSIM	0.758	0.953	0.952	0.946	0.942	0.927	0.913	0.939	0.936	0.929	0.940	0.953
	HVS	20.336	20.427	21.25 3	21.21 8	21.30 6	21.13 3	24.531	21.23 1	21.30 7	21.01 1	21.081	24.531
	HVS m	22.007	21.670	22.55 4	22.60 6	22.70 7	22.41 8	26.453	22.60 3	22.73 3	22.28 1	22.401	26.453
Img5	PSN R	30.918	34.782	34.33 7	34.28 5	34.07 2	34.51 4	35.281	34.12 6	33.83 3	34.87 4	34.328	35.281
	Ciela b	2.539	1.955	2.146	1.903	1.990	2.033	1.817	2.034	2.031	1.917	2.049	1.817
	SSIM	0.677	0.928	0.903	0.917	0.917	0.907	0.831	0.914	0.910	0.920	0.890	0.928
	HVS	27.739	27.778	28.16 3	28.14 4	28.07 1	28.42 8	30.870	28.17 1	28.02 1	28.21 3	28.219	30.870
	HVS m	29.436	29.212	29.63 2	29.66 7	29.69 8	29.90 9	32.173	29.70 5	29.67 1	29.66 0	29.679	32.173
Img6	PSN R	27.796	31.616	31.77 5	30.99 7	30.93 7	31.81 6	32.177	31.21 3	30.64 6	31.74 0	31.315	32.177
	Ciela b	5.508	4.331	4.611	4.230	4.197	4.348	3.619	4.398	4.339	4.385	4.341	3.619
	SSIM	0.720	0.934	0.909	0.913	0.916	0.902	0.874	0.916	0.904	0.898	0.902	0.934
	HVS	24.627	24.620	25.06 8	24.73 9	24.90 3	25.00 2	28.061	25.07 0	24.86 8	25.05 7	24.969	28.061
	HVS m	26.295	26.029	26.48 4	26.31 1	26.42 2	26.41 3	29.485	26.51 2	26.39 5	26.47 4	26.433	29.485
Img7	PSN R	30.561	35.654	35.51 6	34.95 4	34.41 0	35.47 9	34.405	34.45 3	34.06 9	35.51 1	35.273	35.654
	Ciela b	3.598	2.496	2.535	2.554	2.633	2.540	2.374	2.696	2.694	2.524	2.599	2.374
	SSIM	0.741	0.942	0.940	0.933	0.930	0.936	0.882	0.928	0.924	0.936	0.929	0.942
	HVS	27.968	28.420	28.42 0	28.24 5	28.06 9	28.52 8	32.628	28.19 5	27.88 2	28.44 0	28.500	32.628
	HVS m	29.520	29.564	29.56 6	29.48 8	29.34 5	29.68 0	34.727	29.40 2	29.17 6	29.58 8	29.663	34.727
Img8	PSN R	27.013	31.282	31.71 7	30.88 0	30.67 7	31.22 1	30.804	30.76 2	30.41 9	31.33 1	31.015	31.717
	Ciela b	4.658	3.468	3.310	3.536	3.476	3.503	3.051	3.546	3.534	3.449	3.596	3.051
	SSIM	0.740	0.937	0.937	0.921	0.926	0.923	0.890	0.927	0.921	0.927	0.913	0.937
	HVS	24.453	23.969	25.01 5	24.81 1	24.91 6	25.06 0	29.237	24.95 5	24.90 7	24.88 9	24.909	29.237
	HVS m	26.129	25.317	26.42 0	26.32 6	26.41 6	26.45 5	31.046	26.41 5	26.42 5	26.26 4	26.311	31.046
Img9	PSN R	29.869	32.768	33.33 8	32.63 6	32.07 8	33.41 4	34.743	32.82 3	31.91 2	33.40 7	32.908	34.743
	Ciela b	3.037	2.555	2.462	2.437	2.811	2.371	2.078	2.539	2.892	2.371	2.457	2.078
	SSIM	0.512	0.665	0.668	0.653	0.653	0.618	0.636	0.609	0.594	0.619	0.651	0.668
	HVS	26.315	25.823	26.77 0	26.60 7	26.78 7	26.78 1	30.702	26.83 3	26.76 8	26.81 4	26.668	30.702
	HVS m	27.938	27.232	28.18 1	28.12 1	28.27 7	28.19 2	32.204	28.28 5	28.26 5	28.22 9	28.097	32.204
Img10	PSN R	27.156	31.142	31.37 3	30.60 0	30.49 1	31.21 2	32.149	30.53 8	30.20 9	31.16 1	30.910	32.149
	Ciela b	4.755	3.702	3.688	3.630	3.639	3.703	3.025	3.875	3.717	3.665	3.671	3.025
	SSIM	0.696	0.916	0.916	0.903	0.905	0.881	0.829	0.905	0.899	0.904	0.894	0.916
	HVS	24.115	23.899	24.40 5	24.19 2	24.20 9	24.36 5	29.045	24.32 7	24.11 2	24.42 4	24.404	29.045
	HVS m	25.720	25.235	25.73 8	25.70 3	25.67 7	25.70 4	30.552	25.69 3	25.59 4	25.76 3	25.790	30.552
Img11	PSN R	29.136	32.760	33.04 3	32.33 6	32.37 0	32.99 8	32.289	32.46 6	32.18 1	33.02 6	32.385	33.043
	Ciela b	4.238	3.313	3.300	3.430	3.378	3.278	3.265	3.424	3.427	3.276	3.385	3.265
	SSIM	0.731	0.919	0.919	0.902	0.911	0.914	0.868	0.910	0.906	0.916	0.898	0.919
	HVS	26.758	26.210	27.10 8	26.99 6	27.08 3	27.07 4	29.120	27.06 7	27.05 9	27.08 0	27.104	29.120
	HVS m	28.408	27.623	28.52 4	28.53 6	28.57 4	28.47 4	30.554	28.53 0	28.56 4	28.47 9	28.531	30.554
Img12	PSN R	25.977	29.260	30.25 5	29.75 8	29.75 6	29.91 5	30.136	29.71 1	29.59 5	29.89 4	29.716	30.255
	Ciela b	4.472	3.408	3.272	3.327	3.348	3.475	2.983	3.486	3.409	3.473	3.344	2.983
	SSIM	0.778	0.940	0.942	0.933	0.932	0.914	0.910	0.920	0.918	0.915	0.932	0.942
	HVS	24.186	23.100	24.70 2	24.75 0	24.76 1	24.52 0	28.263	24.63 0	24.72 0	24.52 3	24.646	28.263
	HVS	25.815	24.465	26.07	26.18	26.19	25.85	29.911	26.04	26.16	25.85	26.020	29.911

	m			4	4	5	2		7	7	6		
Average	PSNR	28.426	32.195	32.437	31.810	31.590	32.283	32.398	31.764	31.355	32.355	31.974	32.437
	Cielab	4.283	3.268	3.278	3.260	3.332	3.303	2.949	3.388	3.403	3.270	3.308	2.949
	SSIM	0.715	0.905	0.899	0.890	0.892	0.883	0.852	0.888	0.881	0.888	0.882	0.905
	HVS	25.468	25.214	25.880	25.727	25.771	25.920	29.086	25.802	25.713	25.846	25.858	29.086
	HVS _m	27.102	26.573	27.260	27.215	27.253	27.295	30.638	27.229	27.211	27.212	27.253	30.638

(a) PSNR

(b) CIELAB

(c) SSIM

(d) HVS and HVS_m

Figure 11. Averaged performance metrics of all the demosaicing results for the ground truth pan case.

Figure 12. The ground truth image and three selected demosaiced images using the ground truth pan case.

3.3. Discussions and Comparisons

We summarize the key results in Tables 2 to 4 and put them into Table 5 and Figure 13. We have the following observations:

- In terms of PSNR, the combination of FOE and GFPCA improved over the combination of LDI-NAT and GSA by 0.11 dB. There is still a somewhat big gap of 0.635 dB between FOE/GFPCA and GT/GSA.
- In terms of CIELAB, the difference between the FOE/GFPCA and LDI-NAT/GSA is 0.033 whereas the difference between GT/GFPCA and FOE/GFPCA is 0.119. Relatively speaking, there is still a gap for further improvement.
- In terms of SSIM, the difference between FOE/Standard and LDI-NAT/Standard is 0.003 and the difference between GT/Standard and FOE/Standard is 0.035.
- In terms of HVS, the difference between FOE/GFPCA and LDI-NAT/GFPCA is 0.117 dB and the difference between GT/GFPCA and FOE/GFPCA is 0.351 dB.
- In terms of HVSm, the difference between FOE/GFPCA and LDI-NAT/GFPCA is 0.002 dB and the difference between GT/GFPCA and FOE/GFPCA is 0.175 dB.

The above observations also answer the two questions raised in Section 1. First, after some extensive experiments, it was found that there do exist better algorithms (FOE and inpaint-nans) than the LDI-NAT method. Second, we also quantify the performance gain of the better algorithms. In short, it appears that the best inpainting algorithm (FOE) closes the gap between the FOE and the ideal case. However, even the demosaicing results with GT pan may still have room for improvement, which will be a future topic to pursue.

Table 5. Demosaicing results

	LDI-NAT for Pan	FOE for Pan	Reference (GT) Pan
Metrics	Metric/ Best PS	Metric/ Best PS	Metric/Best PS
PSNR (dB)	31.692/GSA	31.802/GFPCA	32.437/GSA
CIELAB	3.101/GFPCA	3.068/GFPCA	2.949/GFPCA
SSIM	0.867/Standard	0.870/Standard	0.905/Standard
HVS (dB)	28.618/GFPCA	28.735/GFPCA	29.086/GFPCA
HVSm (dB)	30.465/GFPCA	30.463/GFPCA	30.638/GFPCA

Figure 13. Comparison of the demosaicing results of using different combinations of inpainting and pansharpener algorithms.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we focus on further improving the demosaicing performance of CFA 3.0. Our idea is to see if newer inpainting algorithms can help improve the overall demosaicing performance. Six conventional and deep learning based methods were compared and the FOE method yielded slight better performance than others. One key observation is that there is still room for improvement because, when we used the ground truth pan band, the overall demosaicing performance is much better than what we have right now. Hence, one future direction is to seek better inpainting methods. Another direction is to develop an end-to-end deep learning approach to demosaicing CFA 3.0.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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